

Thermal conductivity reduction in highly-doped cubic SiC by phonon-defect and phonon-electron scattering

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FIG. 1: (a) Electronic band structure, (b) Phonon dispersion obtained from LDA and GGA functionals, respectively. The experimental results are also shown for comparison [1, 2].

I. BAND STRUCTURE AND PHONON DISPERSION

In Fig. 1, the band structure of the pristine system is shown and the calculated band gap is 1.34 eV. On the other hand, we have calculated the phonon dispersion by using real space finite-difference method with a $5 \times 5 \times 5$ supercell, reaching a good agreement with experimental data [1, 2]. The lack of imaginary frequencies indicates a stable structure. We have also tried the GGA functional to calculate phonon dispersion. However, that only leads to a slight underestimation of optical phonon frequencies as compared to those from LDA and to experimental results. Since the phonon dispersion from LDA functional agrees better with the experiments, LDA functional is adopted in our work.

II. PHONON-DEFECT SCATTERING RATES VS SUPERCELL SIZE

In the Fig. 2, we show the phonon-defect scattering rates by B and N defects for both neutral and charged cases calculated with $4 \times 4 \times 4$ and $5 \times 5 \times 5$ supercells, respectively. It is found that phonon-defect scattering rates in each case are almost converged with a $5 \times 5 \times 5$ supercell, which was used in the main text.

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FIG. 2: Phonon-defect scattering rates of (a) neutral B_C^0 , (b) charged B_C^{-1} , (c) neutral N_C^0 and (d) charged N_C^{+1} defects, each calculated with $4 \times 4 \times 4$ and $5 \times 5 \times 5$ supercells, respectively.

III. COMPUTATIONAL DETAILS OF B- AND N-DOPED 4H-SiC

We performed the structural optimization of the perfect 4H-SiC system using the VASP density functional theory (DFT) package [3], with the projector-augmented-wave method and local density approximation (LDA) to the exchange and correlation functional. Next, the Phonopy package [4] was used to calculate the harmonic IFCs of perfect structures with 3

FIG. 3: (a) Phonon dispersion along the high symmetry path for 4H-SiC, (b) the cumulative thermal conductivity curves with respect to phonon frequencies along a-axis and c-axis, respectively.

$\times 3 \times 2$ supercells and Γ -sampling. The calculated phonon dispersion is shown in Fig. 3(a). For the anharmonic third-order IFCs, the `thirdorder.py` code in ShengBTE package [5] was used, also with a $3 \times 3 \times 3$ supercell and Γ -sampling, as well as a cutoff of 3.3 \AA in the interaction range.

The ph-def scattering rate calculations for neutral and ionized defects were executed using the `almaBTE` code [6]. We first employed a $3 \times 3 \times 2$ supercell with one specific defect replacing the hexagonal site (*h*-site) of carbon atoms to perform structural relaxation. The Phonopy package was then used to extract harmonic IFCs of this defective supercell. The Green's functions of the perfect system were calculated on a $19 \times 19 \times 6$ grid using the tetrahedron method to integrate over the Brillouin-zone and the ph-def scattering rates were then calculated with a $23 \times 23 \times 7$ \mathbf{q} -grid.

With regard to the calculation of ph-el scattering rates, electron-phonon coupling matrix elements were first calculated on coarse $6 \times 6 \times 2$ \mathbf{k} - and \mathbf{q} -grids with the Quantum Espresso DFT package [7]. We then interpolated them onto denser $46 \times 46 \times 14$ \mathbf{k} -grid and $23 \times 23 \times 7$ \mathbf{q} -grid, respectively, through the Wannier function interpolation method as implemented in the EPW package [8].

After ph-def and ph-el scattering were determined, the exploration of bulk κ is straightforward. This was implemented in a modified version of the ShengBTE package [5] using a $23 \times 23 \times 7$ \mathbf{q} -grid to ensure convergence of κ . The intrinsic thermal conductivity at 300 K in 4H-SiC is converged as 446 and 378 $\text{Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ along the a - and c -axes, respectively, which are closed to previous results [9]. From Fig. 3(b), we can see that the thermal conductivity is completely contributed from phonon modes at frequencies below 115 rad/ps.

Finally, we also employed the similar approach in the main text to estimate carrier concentration for n -doped 4H-SiC. The parameters involved in the calculation are taken from experiments. m_e^* is taken as $0.77m_0$ with free electron mass m_0 [10], the band gap ($E_c - E_v$) is 3.263 eV [11] and the ionization energy of N defects is 0.066 eV [12]. By solving Eq.(11) in the main text self-consistently, free electron concentrations at 300 K, can be obtained as $7 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ for the doping level of 10^{20} cm^{-3} .

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